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Validated geographic search filters for bibliographic databases: a scoping review

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Background: The number of scientific publications has considerably increased. Measures to reduce search and screening efforts can enhance the efficiency of systematic review preparation. Search filters are valuable tools for identifying reports with shared characteristics in bibliographic databases. Geographic search filters limit literature search results to a specific geographic characteristic (e.g. a country or region). Searching the literature using geographic filters can, for example, be useful to provide an overview of cultural, epidemiological, or health economics aspects or to indicate inequalities in health care in a certain region.

Objective: Our aim was to identify validated geographic search filters and report on their development and performance measures.

Methods: Following JBI methodology, we conducted a scoping review of validation studies for search filters targeting reports from or about specific geographic areas, such as individual countries/regions or groups of countries/regions. The literature search took place in August 2023 and was performed in PubMed, EMBASE, InterTASC Information Specialists' Sub-Group (ISSG), and Google Scholar. No language or publication date restrictions were applied. Two reviewers independently conducted the selection process, including abstract and full-text screening, using the Rayyan App. Two reviewers independently extracted data, followed by comparison and narrative synthesis. Data extraction included the basic characteristics of the geographic search filters (e.g., country/region, database), methods used for its development and validation, and performance measures (sensitivity, precision, number needed to read (NNR) and specificity).

Results: Our literature search yielded 907 hits. We included nine reports that addressed six search filters for the following geographic regions: Spain, the African continent, the United Kingdom, OECD countries, the United States, and publications from German-speaking countries in high-ranking nursing journals. The methods used for developing geographic search filters were heterogeneous. Gold standard sets were developed using database searches (3/6) and relative recall methods (3/6). Only three filters were developed using objective methods and two underwent internal validation. The sensitivity of the search filters ranged from 73% to nearly 100%, with precision varying between 9.4% and 88%. The NNR ranged from 1.1 to 469, while specificity ranged from 82.7% to 100%. Performance measures were inconsistently reported, and calculation methods varied.

Implication for research and/or (healthcare) practice: The results indicate that validated geographic search filters are limited. The identified filters facilitated the development of a search filter for Germany [1] and may contribute to the development of further geographic search filters. Standardized methods and consistent reporting are crucial for the future development and validation of geographic search filters.

Sources:

[1] Pachanov A, Muentz C, Hirt J, Pieper D. Development and validation of a geographic search filter for MEDLINE (PubMed) to identify studies about Germany. *Res Synth Methods*. 2024;15(6):1147-60.